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Research Article

**NEGATIVE EFFECTS OF INTERNET ON INDEXES THE
MANTEL HEALTH OF NURSING STUDENTS****Mahfoudh F. Hassan, Luay Abdulwahid Shihab***

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Abstract:

To identify the negative effect level of internet for nursing students, types of websites and hours of using internet by students. Compare between the sex [male & female] and site [center & out] of city in the hours of using. Relationship between hours & types of websites with mental health index. Study instrument Structured questionnaire was used for the purpose of the data collection by Three ratings [always, sometimes, never]. As well it consist of [25] to negative effect of internet and its levels. Project's sample had [40.90 %] negative effects of internet, this was acceptable according test questioner. More using types of website by students were each of social media and science sites. Average of hours in using of internet was [4.78] hours per day. There is significant relationship between negative effect of internet and Number of hours in use.

Keywords: internet, Negative effects of internet, mantel health, nursing students**Corresponding author:****Luay Abdulwahid Shihab,**

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INTRODUCTION:

The Internet is the largest network of computers with a set of computers connected to each other in different regions of the world by personal computers and local networks and international networks, so that anyone can become a member of this network as he provided the requirements that make him a line within the network [1]. Which enables it to obtain a huge amount of information when searching for any topic using search sites, whether at home or office. The World Wide Web has provided a tremendous development with a number of advantages and disadvantages. The Internet, like most inventions, is a two-edged sword [2]. As all individuals and networks included within them are working to disseminate information via the Internet. It is one of the world's most widely distributed communications networks that allows community members to exchange messages and data, making the world a small village where anyone anywhere in the world can communicate with others anywhere through a small device like a computer or mobile phone. Despite the rapid growth of internet users in recent years, come questions are posed regarding its effects on humans, since improper use of the Internet has caused users to develop problematic behaviors and exhibit many psychological effects [3]. A negative consequence arising from improper use of the internet and internet games are their impact on mental health. Mental health refers to successful mental functioning, which results in constructive activities socialization, and bolstering learning abilities and self-confidence. This is of great significance to adolescents, as using effective social interactions is essential for behavioral, emotional adaptation and successful functioning. Children and adolescent socialization ability improve their communication skills and makes them more receptive to social influence, and grow better with good communication skills. Effective communication makes individuals prosperous and improves the quality of their relationships. The results of some studies show that although the internet has been introduced as an amazing technology, it has negative effects on individuals' social life, and communication skills. Using the Internet reduces people's motivation for interacting with each other, thereby causing them to spend less time in the company of friends and family members with subsequent isolation and depression. Moreover, the internet [4].

2-1 Internet Usage'

The use of the Internet has become a central part of the developed and developing societies around the world. Approximately 78.1 percent of the United

States population use Internet on a regular basis [Internet World Stats, 2012]. Close to 245 million people uses Internet in United States, ranking among top ten countries in the world with highest Internet usage. According to the study of Shana [2012] students' intention of using internet mainly for making friends and chatting, and only a few percentages [260] of students use internet for academic purposes. Young 2004 [5]. investigated the effect of internet use and social capital on the academic performance of the students. The study commented that internet usage has less effect on studies and students are more rely on the internet to access information and entertainment. The study conducted Jeong [2005] [5]. demonstrated that internet addiction is significantly and negatively affect students' academic performance.

2-2 Actual and Perceived Internet Usage'

The Internet based technology has been changing rapidly over the last three decades, and has significantly changed the online digital business [6]. for example, a significant proportion of transactions in business to business and business to customer environment use Internet based, placing orders, financial transactions etc. Students are not immune to this change; they have access to increased Internet based applications than a decade ago. In addition, increased numbers of students gain access to the Internet each year and arguments have been made by researchers about their academic performance being influenced, both positively and negatively with the increased use of the Internet [7]. Several studies have focused on the actual and the 'perceived role of the Internet has played on the student's academic performance. Very few studies have focused on the actual role of the Internet [based on the actual hours spent on the Internet] on student academic performance. Recent and past studies have shown negative association between academic outcomes and the use of electronic media [includes offline and online media usage], students would perform poorly with increased use of the electronic media [8].

2-3 Nonmedical Internet Use

Excessive use of the Internet for gaming and gambling has been [9]. as has use of the Internet for tied to increased depression shopping. While suggestive of possible negative outcomes from using the Internet for entertainment, these studies have primarily been done as case studies of addicted individuals and/or as evidence for Internet pathology. It is not clear whether less excessive amounts of Internet use for these purposes would have similar

negative outcomes. Finally, use of the Internet for escape may have both positive and negative outcomes, resulting in the overall impact on well-being remaining relatively neutral. Going online to escape and relax has been shown to be a source of gratification to Internet users and is a predictor of heavier Internet usage[10]. This may have positive well-being outcomes since using the Internet to escape and relax may be viewed as a coping strategy or as a restorative activity that helps people “recharge batteries” On the other hand, individuals likely to say that they use the Internet for escapism are often doing so to alleviate feelings of depression and isolation or to divert themselves from something stressful and negative going on in the offline world [eg, HIV treatment][11]. Again, this may be beneficial as a coping strategy and/or relaxation technique, but if this escapism occurs at pathological levels it may also lead to harmed sociorelationships, negative health consequences [from a lack of activity], and further depression.

2-4 Negative Effects of the Internet

1. Internet Benefit

The ease of transferring information through this network has made it rich in the knowledge that the individual aspires to acquire. It has become a quick reference to knowledge. This is done by search engines that allow the individual to search for the desired data and give him a huge range of results.

- The network provided the ability to transfer images and sounds, which facilitated the process of documenting and confirming data.
- Created a new area for remote communication where it allowed a picture to accompany the sound so that it is possible to see individuals who are away from you thousands of kilometers through software that interacts with the network to allow communication and voice and image transmission.

- Create a new method of e-mail, allowing individuals to send and receive messages through the Internet, and the transmission is characterized by the enormous speed between sending and receiving messages, and may contain e-mails and various forms of data.

2. Internet disadvantages

The Internet has many benefits, but if it is used incorrectly, it becomes more negative than its advantages.

- It wastes time so that its users reach addiction.
- Dealing with and identifying bad companions.
- Neglect of the Internet user for his social life and family and functional obligations.

- Leads to some mental disorders such as trembling, continuous finger movements, and leads to anxiety, excessive thinking of the Internet and what happens there, feeling sad and depressed.

3. Loss of the human touch

People absorbed in their activities online tend to forget that there are real people in their surroundings who need their attention or have socialization needs. Social networking gives more importance to virtual friends than real ones.

4. Criminal elements use information to advance their malicious internets.

Internet users can fall victim to criminal elements who meddle with their emails or do something nasty with their credit card information. Phishing or fooling other people into believing that criminal-owned websites are legitimate led to millions of money lost to misleading business transactions.

5. Abandonment of family

In one instance, a couple in Korea was preoccupied with their virtual baby forgetting to feed their real baby who died of hunger. People become insensitive as they are absorbed by the hidden hand of the internet into its lair. Considering that the effects of the internet to people can be both positive and negative; there is a need to manage this technology for man's overall benefit. Of foremost concern is the need to make sure that internet security is well in place to prevent the negative effects of the internet to innocent people [11].

2-5 Effects of social networking and behavior

Evgeny Morozov has said that social networking could be potentially harmful to people. He writes that they can destroy privacy, and notes that "Insurance companies have accessed their patients' Facebook accounts to try to disprove they have hard-to-verify health problems like depression; employers have checked social networking sites to vet future employees; university authorities have searched the web for photos of their students' drinking or smoking pot." He also said that the Internet also makes people more complacent and risk averse. He said that because much of the ubiquity of modern technology—cameras, recorders, and such—people may not want to act in unusual ways for fear of getting a bad name. People can see pictures and videos of you on the Internet, and this may make you act differently [].

2-6 Addiction” and Internet Addiction Disorder

The consumption of any psychoactive drug legal or illegal can be thought of as comprising three stages:

Use, Abuse and Addiction [4]. Initially the user may consume the drug simply to strain the resulting pleasurable or other beneficial effects. If use of the drug then escalates to the point where it is interfering with the ability of the user to function normally, use may turn into abuse, and if drug consumption increases further the user may become addicted. Kimberly S. Young conducted a study involving nearly 500 heavy internet users. McMuran [1994] pointed out that addictive behavior fluctuates and moves in and out routinely and not necessarily progressive in nature, because the level of involvement depends upon the current situation and the addict's skill for coping with that situation. Kraut, Patterson, Lundmark, Kielser, Muknopadhy and Seherlis [1998] revealed that Internet is negatively influencing our real life strong ties and is displacing our social activity.

2-7 What Causes an Addiction to Computers or the Web?

Whenever Internet addicts feel overwhelmed, stressed, depressed, lonely or anxious, they use the Internet to seek solace and escape. Studies from the University of Iowa Show that Internet addiction is quite common among males ages 20 to 30 years old who are suffering from depression.

Certain people are predisposed to having a computer or Internet addiction, such as those who suffer from anxiety and depression. Their lack of emotional support means they turn to the Internet to fill this need. There are also those who have a history of other types of addiction, such as addictions to alcohol, drugs, sex and gambling. Even being stressed and unhappy can contribute greatly to the development of a computer or Internet addiction. People who are overly and cannot easily relate to their peers are also at a higher risk of developing a computer or Internet addiction.

2-8 Social Networking Websites and Health

Every human being fear is having health problems. Once someone has health issues, his or her life will be affected. Therefore, people need to be careful and cherish their good health. Nowadays, a health issue, not only comes from the so called environment of the person, but also within the web 2.0 environment. In the previous years the main discussion issue was the addiction to television, today's issues deal with internet addiction and the increased amount of time young people and adults spend on searching the internet. Internet use plays in the lives of today's young adults, understanding possible health implications is of clinical importance. In particular, problematic Internet use [PI U] is a new and growing

health concern for adolescents and young adults. PI U lacks a standardized definition, but it has also been referred to as internet addiction [7].

2-9 Top 14 Negative Effects Of Internet On Student .

Internet is a useful tool in technology era. However, it still remains many negative aspects if it is abused by people especially student and children. Here are [6] negative effects of internet on students that people should know to avoid :

1. Addiction
2. Work Ethic
3. Cyber Crimes
4. Abandonment Of Family
5. Physical Development
6. Cyber Bully
7. Privacy Disrupted
8. Cheating
9. Lazy
10. Bad Webs
11. Hesitant Toward Face To Face Communication
12. Lacking Creativity And Dependence
13. Wastage Of Time
14. Insomnia

3-1 Design of the study:

Descriptive design was carried out to evaluate of student knowledge about negative effective of internet .

3-2 setting of the study :

The study was conducted at University of Basra - college of nursing ---- 2016 2017 .

3-3 the sample of the study :

Sample of 146 students [first, second, third & fourth year] in college of nursing in University of Basra . Where number of male was [36], number of female was [110].

3-4 Study instrument :

Structured questionnaire was used for the purpose of the data collection by Three ratings [always, sometimes, never]. As well it consist of [25] to negative effect of internet. and its levels.

3-5 Methods of data collection :

Data were gathered by research through structural interview with students by the use of questionnaire. Data collection was carried out from December 2017 through 2 weeks .

3-6 Statically analysis

Analysis was made by using SPSS Version 16, [arithmetic mean, standard deviation, standard error,

percent, t-test and Pearson correlation].

4- RESULTS OF STUDY AND ITS DISCUSSION:

4-1 Levels the negative effects of internet

Table 1: negative effects score on students – total test score equal 100

Negative effects score	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
12	2	1.4	1.4
14	2	1.4	2.7
16	5	3.4	6.2
18	1	0.7	6.8
20	1	0.7	7.5
22	4	2.7	10.3
24	3	2.1	12.3
26	4	2.7	15.1
28	5	3.4	18.5
30	7	4.8	23.3
32	10	6.8	30.1
34	11	7.5	37.7
36	13	8.9	46.6
38	7	4.8	51.4
40	9	6.2	57.5
42	7	4.8	62.3
44	6	4.1	66.4
46	4	2.7	69.2
48	10	6.8	76.0
50	5	3.4	79.5
52	2	1.4	80.8
54	7	4.8	85.6
56	2	1.4	87.0
60	3	2.1	89.0
62	2	1.4	90.4
64	2	1.4	91.8
66	3	2.1	93.8
68	1	0.7	94.5
70	1	0.7	95.2
74	2	1.4	96.6
82	2	1.4	97.9
84	2	1.4	99.3
86	1	0.7	100.0
Total	146	100.0	

Table [1] shows student's negative effects scores where maximum degree [86], minimum degree [12] and the more frequency was [36] degree have [13] students as percent [8.9 %].

Table 2: Student's negative effects test

Variable	N	minimum	maximum	mean	Std deviation	Total test score	result
Negative effect	146	12	86	40.90	15.435	100	normal

Table [2] shows student's negative effects test for [146] nursing college student in the questionnaire, where minimum degree equal [12], maximum degree equal [86], the mean of negative effect equal [40.90], std. deviation equal [15.435] and its result evaluation was in normal level. this result and its level give idea to nursing student awareness about the negative effect of internet .

4-2 Result using a types of websites and Hours of using internet

Table 3: using a types of websites by sample

Types of internet	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
1- Social media	24	16.4	16.4
2- Science sites	17	11.6	28.1
3- Each above	94	64.4	92.5
4- Anthers	11	7.5	100.0
Total sample	146	100.0	

Table [3] this table shows using a types of websites by sample, where more type have used social media & science site by students at [94 %] percent. This result and its Frequency give us idea of nursing student's to internet web sites.

Table 4: Hours of using of the internet

Hours	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
0	1	0.7	0.7
1	22	15.1	15.8
2	24	16.4	32.2
3	21	14.4	46.6
4	22	15.1	61.6
5	12	8.2	69.9
6	12	8.2	78.1
7	6	4.1	82.2
8	7	4.8	87.0
9	2	1.4	88.4
10	8	5.5	93.8
12	3	2.1	95.9
13	1	0.7	96.6
14	1	0.7	97.3
15	1	0.7	97.9
23	1	0.7	98.6
24	2	1.4	100.0
Total	146	100.0	

This table [4] shows the hours of internet using, by nursing students where less frequency have [1] student in the rate of percent [0.7 %] at zero hour per day , more frequency have [24] students in the rate of percent [16.4 %] at two hours per day .

4-3 Result comparison to sex [male & female] and sit [center & out] of city in hours of using

Table 5: Comparison to sex [male & female]

variables	N	hours	mean	Std. deviation	Std. Error Mean	T-value	P-value	result
sex	36	Male	6.17	5.24	0.87	2.36	0.02	significant
sit	110	Female	4.33	3.59	0.40	0.99	0.32	insignificant

At level [0.05] and degree of freedom = 144.

The table [5] shows comparison to sex [male & female] and Housing site [city center & out center] in hours of using, t-value to deferent between male & female [2.36] is significant at 0.05 level. T-value to deferent between city center & out center [0.99] is insignificant at level[0.05].

4-4 Results the relationship between hours & types of websites with mental health index

Table 6: the correlation between hours & types of using with mental health index

Pearson correlation [R]					
Variables	Mental health Index [R-value]	Df [n-2]	P-value	Result	N
Hours of using	0.347	144	0.000	Significant	146
Types of websites	0.056	144	0.499	Insignificant	146

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level [2-tailed].

The relationship between hours & types of websites with mental health index hours of using for mental health index [0.347] ,Df [144] , P-value [0.000] so the result significant , Types of websites Variables for mental health index [0.056] ,Df [144] , P-value [0.499] so the result insignificant [Table [6]].

4-5 Discussion of the result in table [2]

Result evaluation of student was in normal level. This result and its level give us idea to nursing Students as the following

- 1- Nursing Students' awareness about the negative effect of internet .
- 2- Nursing students have the right way to use the Internet .
- 3- The treatment of nursing students with the questionnaire of the negative impact of the Internet was positive and realistic .

in table [3] result using 21 types of websites by students and its Frequencygive us idea about a nursing Students' to internet web sites. It sortsocial

media & science sits by students at [94 %] percent because Attention and specialization of nursing students in the field of health .

Nursing is a profession within the health care sector focused on the care of individuals, families, and communities so they may attain, maintain, or recover optimal health and quality of life. Nurses may be differentiated from otherhealth care providers by their approach to patient care, training, and. scope ofpractice19.20

Nurse education consists of the theoretical and practical training provided tonurses with the purpose to prepare them for their duties as nursing care professionals. This education is provided to nursing students by experiencednurses and other medical professionals who have qualified or experienced for educational tasks. Most countries offer nurse education courses that can be relevant to general nursing or to specialized areas including mental health nursing, pediatric nursing and post-operative nursing 21.

In table [5] the relationship between hours & types of websites with mental health index, where the between the number of hours at internet with mental health index was significant because for the following :

1- Mental health is negatively effected by the number 0 Internet use .

2- Regular use of the Internet leads to healthy mental health

Some research employs studying brain functions in Internet users. Some studies assert that these changes are harmful 22.

In an August 2008 article in The Atlantic ["Is Google Making Us Stopped?"], Nicholas Carr experientially asserts that using the Internet can lead to lower attention span and make it more difficult to read in the traditional sense [that is, read a book at length without mental interruptions]. He says that he and his friends have found it more difficult to concentrate and read wholebooks even though they read a great deal when they were younger [that is, when they did not have access to the Internet] 23.

5-1 CONCLUSIONS:

1- Project's sample had [40.90] negative effect of internet, this was acceptable according test questioner.

2- More using types of website by students were each of 50 media and science sites .

3-Average of hours in using of internet was [4.78] hours per day .

4- Male was more hours stay at internet compare to female as significant, but non-significant between city center and its out .

5- There is significant relationship between negative effect of internet and Number of hours in use .

6- There is internet and type of using .

5-2 RECOMMENDATIONS:

1-Adoption of the questionnaire in determining the negative impact of the Internet on the students.

2- Take the results of the study in diagnosing the damage of the Internet to students.

3- Continuous guidance for students to damage the internet.

4- Conducting a study to expose the damage of the Internet to social relations.

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